

1-Phenyl-3-thiobenzoylthiocarbamide as a Reagent for Extraction and Photometric Determination of Lead, Zinc and Mercury

D. P. AMBHORE and A. P. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 8 February 1984, revised 31 December 1984, accepted 11 September 1985

Extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} using 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoylthiocarbamide (PTT) is described. Pb-PTT complex is extractable in benzene whereas Zn-PTT and Hg-PTT complexes are extractable in chloroform, showing maximum absorbance at 385, 400 and 395 nm, respectively. Quantitative extraction of lead and mercury is obtained at pH 5.5 while for zinc it is at 6.0. The methods are simple and can be used satisfactorily for determination of these metals in various samples, such as ores, alloys, drugs, petrol, paint and solder.

THE use of 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoylthiocarbamide (PTT) as an analytical reagent is being thoroughly investigated in our laboratory, and estimation of copper¹, cobalt and nickel² and iron³ has already been reported. The present work reports a systematic investigation into the analysis of lead, zinc and mercury with PTT and extension of developed methods to the estimation of these metals in various samples. The analysis of these metals has been of interest and various photometric methods have been suggested for determination of Pb⁴⁻⁶, Zn⁷⁻⁹ and Hg¹⁰⁻¹².

The methods developed in the present studies are simple, convenient and rapid and can be used for routine analysis. The reactions are fairly selective and sensitive also.

Experimental

A Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer was used for spectrophotometric measurements. Stock solutions (1.0×10^{-2} M) of lead, zinc and mercury were prepared by dissolving a known weight of A.R. grade lead nitrate, zinc sulphate and mercuric chloride respectively, in double-distilled water. The working solutions were prepared by proper dilution of stock solutions. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. The reagent PTT was prepared in the laboratory^{1,13} and purified. The reagent is stable. Freshly prepared reagent solution was always used in the studies.

General procedure :

Lead : An aliquot of solution (100 μ g Pb) was taken in a beaker and its pH was adjusted to 5.5 ± 0.1 with HCl/NaOH in a total volume of 20 ml. To it was then added 7.35×10^{-5} M PTT (5 ml) (M : R = 1 : 4) in acetone. The mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min for full colour development of

the yellowish red Pb-PTT complex. It was transferred to a separatory funnel and equilibrated for 1 min with benzene (10 ml). The organic layer was separated and its absorbance was read at 385 nm against a reagent blank. The concentration of lead in an unknown solution was calculated with the help of a calibration graph.

Zinc : An aliquot of solution (50 μ g Zn) was taken and its pH was adjusted to 6.0 ± 0.1 with HCl/NaOH in a total volume of 20 ml. To it was added alcoholic solution of 1.47×10^{-4} M PTT (5 ml) (M : R = 1 : 5). The mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min for full colour development and then equilibrated with CHCl₃ (5 ml). The absorbance of organic layer was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank.

Mercury : An aliquot of solution containing (100 μ g Hg) was taken in a beaker. Acetate buffer (10 ml) of pH 5.5 was added to it and total volume was made to 25 ml with distilled water. The solution was then taken in a separatory funnel and equilibrated with solution of 1.47×10^{-4} M PTT (5 ml) (M : R = 1 : 7) in CHCl₃ for 1 min. The organic layer was separated and its absorbance was measured at 395 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

In all cases complexation occurs in cold condition. The lead-PTT complex is stable for 3 h whereas complexes of Zn and Hg are stable for 5 h as is evident from absorbance studies. Quantitative extraction of Pb and Hg is obtained from pH 5.0 to 6.0. The absorbance was found to be decreasing below pH 5.0 and above pH 6.0. In case of Zn, quantitative extraction occurs from pH 6.0 to 8.0, and beyond this range it showed decrease in absorbance. Use of buffers for maintaining pH of aqueous phase to the required value does not

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLEXES

Characteristics	Pb-PTT	Zn-PTT	Hg-PTT
Colour	Yellowish-red	Yellowish-red	Yellowish-red
pH of extraction	5.5 ± 0.1	6.0 ± 0.1	5.5
λ_{max} (nm)	385	400	395
Beer's law ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	1.0–17.5	1.0–14.0	5.0–55.0
Optimum range of determination ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Ringbom plot)	2–15	2–12	10–49
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.033	0.016	0.081
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	6.924×10^4	3.9×10^4	2.46×10^4
Relative mean deviation (%) (From 10 observations)	0.86	0.83	0.49

prove to be satisfactory in case of Pb and Zn systems, whereas in Hg system sodium acetate-acetic acid or $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4\text{-KH}_2\text{PO}_4$ buffer gave satisfactory results. The physicochemical characteristics of the complexes obtained in the investigations are given in Table 1.

The results of extraction of complexes with various solvents are given in Table 2. Chloroform is found to be the best solvent for extraction of the complexes. For extraction of Pb-PTT complex benzene is found to be equally suitable solvent.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENTS ON EXTRACTION

Solvent	% Extraction*		
	Pb-PTT	Zn-PTT	Hg-PTT
Chloroform	100	100	100
Benzene	100	60.0	94.0
Carbon tetrachloride	52.0	42.0	88.0
Toluene	44.0	Negligible	88.0
Isobutyl methyl ketone	35.0	8.0	62.0
Ethyl acetate	51.0	9.0	15.0

* In a single extraction.

Several foreign ions were examined for their effect on the extraction behaviour of Pb, Zn and Hg. The standard procedure was followed and in each case a known amount of foreign ion solution was added. The tolerance limit for various ions in the determination of 100 μg Pb, 50 μg Zn and 100 μg Hg are given below (figures in parenthesis are in mg and for Pb, Zn and Hg systems, respectively) for a $\pm 2\%$ variation of absorbance: Ni^{II} (none, none, 150), Cu^{II} (none, none, none), Zn^{II} (500**, –, 250), Co^{II} (none, none, 500), Pb^{II} (–, none, 100), Sn^{II} (400, 250, 400), Sb^{III} (400, 250, 250), Bi^{III} (400, 425, 450), Fe^{III} (500**, 112, 250), Al^{III} (400, 450, 500), chloride (2000, 1500, high), iodide (1200, 1600, 4450), thiocyanate (870, 580, 1450), cyanide (3000, none, none), oxalate (1320, 88, 2200), citrate (500, 200, 200), tartrate (200, 1480, 2000), EDTA (none, none, none), Ag^{I} (200, 103, 500), Mn^{II} (400, none, 500) (** masked with cyanide).

Analytical applications :

Determination of lead in solder : An accurately weighed (~ 0.3 g) solder sample (composition : Pb, 60 ; Sn, 40) was taken in a beaker and concentrated

HNO_3 (20 ml) were added. The mixture was heated on a sand-bath until the sample dissolved. The solution was further evaporated almost to dryness. Water was added and made upto 100 ml in a volumetric flask. The solution was further diluted with water so as to give a solution containing nearly 100 μg Pb per ml. Different portions of this solution were taken and analysed by the PTT method as well as by EDTA titration method¹⁴. An average of 5 determinations show that the percentage of lead in solder sample is 58.85% as against 59.10% obtained by EDTA method. The absolute error comes out to be 0.25%.

Determination of lead in ore : Lead ore sample was obtained from Indian Bureau of Mines, Nagpur, which was reported to contain about 58% of lead. The powdered sample (~ 0.4 g) was weighed accurately and dissolved in a mixture of HCl and HNO_3 (15+15 ml). The solution was heated till the nitrous fumes were removed and then evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was treated with a little distilled water. The working solution (~ 100 μg Pb ml^{-1}) was prepared by appropriate dilution of this solution. Lead content was determined by the PTT method. The results were compared with a EDTA titration method¹⁴. The analyses of 5 different sample aliquots show percentage of lead in ore as 56.78% as against 57.05% obtained by the standard EDTA method. The absolute error comes out to be 0.27%.

Determination of lead in petrol : Lead present in petrol as tetraethyl lead, can be freed by treatment of petrol with bromine¹⁵. In the experiment, to petrol sample (100 ml) bromine solution (50 ml) in carbon tetrachloride (30% Br_2 by volume) was added and mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min. It was heated on a hot-plate till bromine evaporated. The remaining solution (~ 40 ml) was cooled and extracted with dilute HNO_3 (two portions of 25 ml each). The aqueous extracts were combined, and bromine water (1 ml) was added and again evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was treated with a little water, filtered and filtrate made to 100 ml. Different portions of this solution were taken and analysed for Pb by the PTT method as well as by standard dithizone method¹⁶. The average concentration of lead in petrol from 5 deter-

minations was found to be 18.66 ppm whereas by dithizone method it comes to be 18.57 ppm. The absolute error is 0.09 and relative error is 0.48%.

Determination of lead in paints : Lead present in paints can also be analysed by this method. The following procedure was adopted. To a weighed sample (~ 0.2 g) in a beaker, concentrated HNO₃ (25 ml) was added. It was heated on a hot-plate and evaporated almost to dryness. To it little distilled water was added, filtered and filtrate made to 100 ml. Different portions of this solution were taken and analysed for Pb by the PTT method as well as by standard dithizone method. There is possibility of the presence of small amounts of Zn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} in paint samples. Their effects can be eliminated by masking them with cyanide¹⁷. This procedure was followed in our studies. From 5 different determinations, lead content in paint sample was found to be 0.52%. By standard dithizone method it comes to be 0.53%. The absolute error is 0.01%.

Determination of zinc in alloys : Standard alloy samples were obtained from the mint of Government of India. An alloy sample (~ 0.2 g) was weighed accurately and dissolved in minimum quantity of concentrated HNO₃. The solution was heated till the nitrous fumes were removed and then evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was treated with a little distilled water and the solution obtained was made to 100 ml. The interference of Cu^{II} was eliminated by precipitating it selectively as sulphide (in acidic medium) and then filtering and analysing the filtrate for zinc with the PTT method as well as with EDTA titration method¹⁴. The average results of 5 such determinations are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF ZINC IN ALLOYS

Alloy no.	Composition (%)			Zn found (%)		Absolute error (%)
	Cu	Zn	Ni	PTT method	EDTA method	
1.	92.0	8.0	—	7.76	7.90	0.14
2.	79.0	20.0	1.0	19.66	19.82	0.16

Determination of zinc in ore : The zinc ore sample was obtained from Indian Bureau of Mines, Nagpur and reported to contain about 55% of zinc. Powdered sample (0.2 to 0.3 g) was weighed accurately and dissolved in a mixture of HCl and HNO₃ (15+15 ml). The solution was heated till all the nitrous fumes were removed and then evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was treated with water, filtered and total volume was made to 100 ml. Zinc content was determined by the PTT method as well as by EDTA titration¹⁴. The analysis of 5 different sample aliquots show the average percentage of zinc in ore as 53.96% as against 54.30% by EDTA titration method. The absolute error comes out to be 0.34%.

Determination of mercury in ointment : Certain drug samples (ointments) contain mercury and use of the PTT method was extended to determination

of mercury in such samples. The following procedure was adopted. An accurately weighed ointment sample was dissolved in CHCl₃ (100 ml) and then extracted with concentrated HCl (two portions of 25 ml each). The solution was evaporated almost to dryness. To it a little distilled water was added, filtered and total volume was made to 100 ml with distilled water. Mercury content was determined by PTT as well as by standard dithizone method. The results obtained are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF MERCURY IN OINTMENTS

Ointment	Manufac'urer	Hg% (certified by supplier)	Hg% found	
			PTT method	Dithizone method
Preparation	H Geoffrey Manners and Co. Ltd.	0.006	0.00592	0.00595
Yellowid	Bell Pharma	0.926	0.912	0.917

The PTT method developed for the determination of Pb, Zn and Hg is very rapid, simple and can be used satisfactorily for analysis of these metals in various samples. In all the cases, colour development takes place in cold and total operation requires only 20 min. In lead system as far as analysis of solder sample is concerned, it is not necessary to remove Sn and Sb (if any) in this method as they are tolerated to a large ratio. The precision and accuracy is also good as compared to some of the methods reported earlier for analysis of solder sample¹⁸ as well as petrol¹⁵. The molar absorptivities of zinc and mercury systems are also comparable with some recently reported methods for the determination of zinc¹⁹ and mercury^{20,21}.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, for encouragement. One of the authors (D.P.A.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- S. Q. R. ILYAS and A. P. JOSHI, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1980, **2**, 263.
- S. Q. R. ILYAS and A. P. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 360.
- S. Q. R. ILYAS and A. P. JOSHI, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1983, **3**, 271.
- W. KUNIHIRO and K. KYOZO, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1976, **25**, 276.
- Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. A. PATEL, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1979, **88**, 1027.
- U. ERHARD and M. RONALD, *Z. Chem.*, 1980, **20**, 149.
- W. HIRTO and Y. NOBUO, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1979, **28**, 154.
- R. B. SINGH, P. JAIN, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *Analyst (London)*, 1979, **104**, 1188.
- B. N. PRABHU and S. M. KHOPKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1034.
- A. K. DE and B. K. PAL, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1979, **2**, 201.
- K. P. SONI, S. P. MATHUR and R. C. CHAUDHARI, *J. Inst. Chem., Calcutta*, 1977, **49**, 33.

12. M. K. GADIA and M. C. MEHRA, *Mikrochem. J.*, 1978, **23**, 278.
13. M. H. DAMLE, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1977.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, New York, 1978, pp. 330, 333.
15. M. E. GRIFRING, A. ROZAK, L. J. SYNDER and S. E. HANDERSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 190.
16. E. B. SANDRELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metal", Interscience, New York, 1950, p. 555.
17. E. HOFFMAN, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **208**, 423.
18. S. B. AKKI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, **45**, 167.
19. P. GOVIL and S. K. BANERJI, *Bull. Inst. Chem. Acad.*, 1977, **24**, 81.
20. A. PANOVA, D. BAKURDZHIEVA and ANGHELOVA, *Dokl. Bolg. Akad. Nauk*, 1977, **30**, 871.
21. P. A. SANCHEZ, P. DIEZ and P. C. GONZALEZ, *Quim. Anal.*, 1977, **31**, 19.